

TYOLOGY OF SOCIOLINGUISTICS

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Abstract: Researches have been created that shed light on the uniqueness of the languages of the world, in a certain sense, and show the different aspects of a particular language from other languages. The main issue of these studies is the interpretation of the relationship between language and society. Studying the aspects of language related to society is important in elucidating the unique internal structure and possibilities of language. During the development of human society, the relation of language to society, which is a means of communication, has been interpreted in different ways. Different opinions, different theories have arisen.

Key words: task, English, Uzbek, theory, linguistics, term, social life.

Being a science between language and society, sociolinguistics studies the following issues:

- 1) society and language are interrelated, proportional historical process and phenomenon.
- 2) as the society progresses, the social functions of the language also improve.
- 3) the vocabulary of the literary language and dialects expands and increases.
- 4) the languages of peoples with close habitats, similar lifestyles and mutual economic relations influence each other. Languages influence not only lexically, but also grammatically.

Some groups understood language as a living organism. Some saw it as an immutable reality. Such views can be summarized as follows by studying them critically and analytically:

1. Language is not a natural-biological phenomenon;
2. The existence of language and its development do not depend on the laws of nature;
3. Language is not related to people's nature, race, or lineage;
4. Only people organized as a society have a language as a means of communication.

Language is a social phenomenon that has arisen on the basis of centuries of historical social experience of human society. Language and society development are inextricably linked. Any reality that occurs in society, in a certain sense, finds its expression in language. The social nature of language is

manifested in its existence in society and serving the interests of society. Sociolinguistics is the main field that analyzes the social nature of language.

This science also deals with the problem of typology of languages. Sociolinguistic typology of languages is a typology that takes into account its social position in society. Such a typology is based on four criteria:

1. Standardization - this means the literary language adopted by speakers of a certain language. The main factor of standardization is the creation of grammar and vocabulary of the language;
 2. Vitality - the presence or absence of a community speaking a certain language is taken into account;
 3. Historicity - this means that as a result of the use of a certain language by society, its moderate and uniform development;
 4. Autonomic means that one or another language that serves as a mother tongue for a certain social group is fundamentally different from other languages in terms of structure, or that one language appears as a variant. For example, when the Uzbek, Kyrgyz, Kazakh, and Karakalpak languages are compared, the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical differences between them are noticeable, which means that these languages are autonomous and independent languages.
- Sociolinguistic classification of languages is carried out on the basis of the above-mentioned typological features. Modern linguists divide languages into the following 7 types from a sociolinguistic point of view: standard languages, creole languages, local languages, classical languages, pidgin languages, artificial languages and dialects.

Now let's talk about the dialect. The word "dialect" is derived from the Greek language, and "dialect" means "dialect".

Several linguists have conducted research in this regard. In particular, from the 20s of the 20th century, European and Russian linguists became seriously interested in this problem. In particular, a number of works began to appear on the classification of society's speech from the point of view of sociolinguistics, the different parameters of the speech of urban and rural residents, the specific characteristics of the speech of craftsmen, workers, and criminal groups. Major sociolinguists conducted serious research on the relationship between society and language, and the relationship between the speaker and the language. They began to recognize that, in addition to the internal structural laws of the language, the way the speaker uses this language, as well as the territorial characteristics of the language, also have social differences.

For example, the famous linguist V. Zhirmunsky, in addition to the division of the existing language in society into regional dialects, also divided it into social dialects. emphasizing that, he writes: "As long as there is a regional dialectology in any language, it must also have a social dialectology." Some scholars call the speech of local peasants a "conditional language". It ranges from the existing form of the language to the conspiratorial slang (conditional language) with certain social characteristics of the language and the language of young children with mechanical ciphers. In general, all the characteristic manifestations of the language limited to the social basis can be included in the social dialect.

If regional dialects arise from the geographical separation of people speaking the same language, social dialects arise from the separation of speakers of the same language in society by social class and field, specialization, age, gender. As Baudouin de Courtenay pointed out, the geographical and social differentiation of the speaker creates a horizontal and vertical division of the language. In other words, regional diversity indicates horizontal division of language, and social diversity indicates vertical division of language. Therefore, when defining a social dialect, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the speaking society belongs to a certain social or professional group, unites as members of a corporation, social class, age, gender, aesthetic, cultural appearance.

In linguistics, the language used by people of a certain social group is defined as a dialect, since any social sphere has a social characteristic, the speech of the people of this social sphere will definitely have a social characteristic. Looking at the problem from this point of view, the language used by people of a certain social sphere can be fully called a social dialect.

In Uzbek linguistics, dialects are approached mainly from a diachronic aspect, and they say that relatively old forms of the literary language have been preserved in this dialect. Sociolinguistics tries to use a synchronic approach with extralinguistic criteria, trying to express the relations carried out by speakers.

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